

BLACK SEA EVOLUTION SINCE THE LAST GLACIAL MAXIMUM BASED ON MICROFAUNAL AND STABLE OXYGEN ISOTOPE RECORDS

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The Black Sea is a semi-enclosed marginal basin, which connects with the Mediterranean Sea through the Bosphorus Strait, Marmara Sea and Dardanelles Strait. Beside the connection with the Mediterranean Sea, in the Late Pliocene-Pleistocene times the Black Sea experienced a period of connection with the Caspian Sea through the Manych Corridor due to the melt waters from the Scandinavian ice sheets (Fedorov, 1977; Major et al., 2006).

In the deeper parts of the Black Sea basin, i.e., below 200 m water depth, Ross and Degens (1974) identified three litho-stratigraphic units (from young to old): Unit 1 (the microlaminated coccolith ooze, deposited under marine conditions), Unit 2 (the sapropel mud, corresponding to an anoxic phase), and Unit 3 (the lacustrine lutite deposited during the freshwater or oligohaline stage).

In the early Holocene, water composition in the Black Sea evolved from brackish to marine; biotical turnover mirrors this change. The transition of the Black Sea from an inland lake to a marine basin during the last glacial/deglacial episode is still generating discussion in the scientific community. In this study, high resolution microfaunal analyses coupled with isotopic and calcium carbonate performed on an AMS ¹⁴C dated core, 09 SG 13 (Fig. 1), revealed changes that occur in the Black Sea from the Last Glacial Maximum through the transition to the present day semi-enclosed marine basin. In the sedimentary record this deglaciation accumulated allochthonous continentally derived red sediments, simultaneous with the global Heinrich Event 1, 18 to 15 kyr BP.

In the studied core (Fig. 1), situated at 200 m water depth, two lithological units, respectively the youngest Unit 1 (Coccolith Mud) and the oldest Unit 3 (Lacustrine lutite), were identified, with the base dated 24.5 kyr BP (into the latter part of Marine Isotope Stage 2, MIS 2, glacial period). Since Unit 2 is missing, either the water depth was not enough to develop the sapropel facies or it was naturally eroded. This gap extends between the Younger Dryas and the mid-Holocene when the brackish Neoeuxinian Lake transformed into a saltwater sea. From the ostracods point of view this transformation is represented by the disappearance of the fresh-brackish ostracod taxa (Caspian in origin) and by the appearance of brackish-marine ones (Mediterranean in origin).

Fig. 1. Location of the analyzed cores

Our study was also focused on shallower sediments recovered with a multicorer from the Romanian Black Sea inner shelf, at the water depth of 78 m (Fig. 1). Based on qualitative and quantitative ostracod analysis, their fluctuation pattern is interpreted in terms of environmental changes.

References

- Fedorov P.V. (1977). Late Quaternary history of the Black Sea and southern seas of Europe. In: Kaplinand, P.A., Shcherbakov, F.A. (Eds.), *Paleogeografiia i otlozheniia pleistotsena iuzhnykh morei SSSR* [Paleogeography and Deposits of the Pleistocene of the Southern Seas of the USSR]. Nauka, Moscow, pp. 25-32 (in Russian)
- Major C.O., Goldstein S.L., Ryan W.B.F., Lericolais G., Piotrowski A.M., Hajdas I. (2006). The co-evolution of Black Sea level and composition through the last Deglaciation and its paleoclimatic significance. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 25: 2031-2047
- Ross D.A., Degens E.T. (1974). Recent sediments of the Black Sea. In: Degens E.T. and Ross D.A. (Eds.), *The Black Sea: Geology, Chemistry, and Biology*. American Association of Petroleum Geologists, Tulsa, USA: 183–199